

Effects of *Helicobacter pylori* Infection on Insulin Resistance in Type 2 Mellitus Diabetics and Non-Diabetics Subjects at Brazzaville University Hospital

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Abstract

Introduction: *H.pylori* infection is the most common bacterial infection worldwide and is associated with gastrointestinal diseases and extra-gastrointestinal pathologies such as diabetes mellitus and insulin resistance. **Objective:** To evaluate insulin resistance in diabetics and non-diabetics

infected with *H. pylori*. **Methods:** We conducted a descriptive cross-sectional study. 90 patients were selected and divided into two groups, 44 patients with T2DM and 46 non-diabetic patients. All information concerning the age and sex of subjects was collected from medical records. Insulin levels were determined by ELISA, blood glucose and HbA1C levels by Cobas c 311, and the HOMA-IR index was calculated. **Results:** The mean age of T2DM patients was 51 ± 11 years, and that of NDT patients 40 ± 15 years. Women (68) predominated over men (22), with a sex ratio of 0.32. The mean values for T2DM patients were: glycemia 12.6 ± 2.3 mmol/l, HbA1C $10.37 \pm 2.9\%$, HOMA-IR 2.69 ± 1.35 ($p < 0.001$), Insulinemia 8.71 ± 3.14 $\mu\text{U/ml}$ ($p = 0.801$). Univariate logistic regression analysis showed: Glycemia OR 2.29 [95% IC 1.80-4.5], HbA1C OR 3.08 [95% IC 0.87-1.02], Insulin OR 1.02 [95% IC 1.0-0.16] and HOMA-IR OR 4.4 [95% IC 0.55-0.95]. Means for NDT infections were: blood glucose 9.7 ± 1.0 mmol/l, insulin 9.7 ± 1.64 $\mu\text{U/ml}$, HOMA-IR 1.45 ± 0.42 , HbA1C $8.6 \pm 0.9\%$. Univariate logistic regression analysis showed: Blood glucose OR 1.1 [95% IC 1.01-2.14], HbA1C OR 1.35 [95% IC 0.08-1.34], Insulin OR 0.51 [95% IC 0.12-1.08], HOMA-IR OR 2.4 [95% IC 0.32-1.45]. **Conclusion:** Our study showed a statistical significant difference between *H. pylori* infection and Insulin resistance, also confirms the link of both.

Abbreviations: T2DM: Type two diabetes of mellitus, NDT: No-Diabetics, OR: Odd ratio.

Introduction

Helicobacter pylori is noninvasive bacterium micro-aerophilic and gram negative which colonize specifically stomach epithelium More than fifty percent of the world's population is infected with *H. pylori*, making it one of the most widespread chronic bacterium infection in the world [1]. More studies have shown that *H. pylori* infection is associated with other severe gastro-intestinal problems, such as chronic gastritis, gastric adenocarcinoma, and MALT lymphoma, which are major worldwide public health issues. Furthermore, its influence on gastro-intestinal disorders, *H. pylori* infection may have a role in developing non-gastrointestinal diseases such as cardiovascular disease and metabolic syndrome, notably diabetes [2]. Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) is a chronic disease non-transmissible which considered today like pandemic disease and is characterized by insulin resistance and beta-pancreatic cells dysfunction. Simon and colleagues explored the first interrelation between *H. pylori* infection and type 2 Diabetes Mellitus in 1982. However, The Insulin Resistance (IR) is a pathologic state in which normal insulin concentrations produce a subnormal response on insulin sensitive tissues coupled with a long-term decline in pancreatic beta cells functions [3-4]. IR and central obesity are the key mechanisms for developing metabolic syndrome (MS) [5]. Several past studies have revealed that a leptin deficiency and a high TNF- α level will induce insulin resistance [6-7]. The relationships between *H. pylori* infection and IR have been reported by more investigations, including two large Japanese population studies and one meta-analysis study [3-8]. *H. pylori* infection may have an impact on insulin resistance, and metabolic syndrome probably because of by elevations in inflammatory markers such as C-reactive protein (CRP) and Interleukin-6 (IL-6) [9]. The main aim in present study was to evaluate the effects

on insulin resistance in diabetes and non-diabetes infected with *H. pylori*.

Materials and Methods

The Gastroenterology and External Medicine Department of Brazzaville University Hospital was chosen for the recruitment and sampling of our patients and the laboratory of the Faculty of Health Sciences for the analysis of the samples. We carried out a descriptive cross-sectional study over a period from June to November 2021. Study population was the male and female subjects with T2DM and non-diabetics.

Sampling Method and Size

We carried out a systematic non-probabilistic sampling among T2DM and non-diabetic patients seen in the Gastroenterology and Internal Medicine department of the University Hospital Center of Brazzaville.

Inclusion Criteria

Included in this study were:

1. The non-diabetic patients of 18 to more years old,
2. T2DM patients of 40 to more years old followed by the Endocrinology and Metabolic diseases service of CHU-Brazzaville and living with diabetes for less than ten years old due to that patients living with diabetes for more ten years old had more diabetics complications than those who had less ten years old according to data from the literature,
3. All consultants in the Gastroenterology and External Medicine consultant service CHU-Brazzaville for gastro-duodenal warning signs making suspect *H. pylori* infection.

Exclusion Criteria

Have not been included in our study patients with:

1. Diabetes mellitus type 1;
2. Patients with hemorrhage digestive;
3. Patients on antibiotic treatment following clarithromycin and amoxicillin as well as a proton pump inhibitor for less months,

4. Others treatments for eradicating *H. pylori* infection.

Blood Collection Procedure

The blood collection was carried out in an Ethyl Diamine Tetra-Acetate (EDTA) tube and in the fluorinated tube and for each patient these three tubes were collected. It was done at the elbow crease in the morning after a 12-hour fast using a vacuite needle by collecting 5 ml of blood in a fluoride tube and in an Ethyle Diamine Tetra tube away from any medication and alcohol intake. The blood collected in the EDTA tube was used for the Glycosylated Hemoglobin (HbA1C) assay and insulin. The blood collected in the fluoride tube was used for the blood sugar measurement.

Blood Sample Processing

After sampling, the samples obtained were transported from the CHU-B sampling location to the laboratory in a cooler containing the cold accumulators. The tubes were then placed on the bench for pretreatment which consisted of leaving the tubes at room temperature. The tubes were centrifuged for 10 minutes at 3,000 rpm. The serums and plasmas obtained were used for the analysis of blood sugar and insulin.

Biochemical Analyzes

The Cobas c 311 was used to measure blood glucose levels. The HbA1c value was determined from blood collected in an EDTA tube using the Cobas c311. The insulin value was determined from plasma collected in an EDTA tube using an ELISA reading.

Homeostasis Model Assessment of Insulin Resistance (HOMA-IR)

The IR index was determined by the HOMA score, which was calculated by the formula:

$$\text{Insulin resistance (HOMA-IR)} = \frac{\text{fasting insulinaemia } (\mu\text{U/mL}) \times \text{fasting glycaemia (mmol/L)}}{22.5} \quad (1)$$

Although there is no a standard normal range of HOMA-IR, the upper cut-off value of HOMA-IR has been proposed between 2.0 and 3.0 in different populations [10, 11, 12, 13, 14]. To avoid using an arbitrary cut-off value, we applied four cut-off values of HOMA-IR index (table 1).

Stool Collection Procedure

We gave the patient a sterile pot containing a spatula and a paper towel while explaining to him the procedure for collecting stools: Collect fresh stools in the morning, defecate on clean mud avoiding contact between urine and stools, take a dab of saddle using the spatula, put a dab of saddle in the sterile jar, close the jar hermetically and put it in the plastic packaging intended for this purpose.

Searching of *H. pylori* Antigen in Stool

The search for the monoclonal antigen of *H. pylori* was performed through rapid stool tests using the JusChek kit. We followed the following steps to search for *H. pylori* in the stool: Unscrew the cap of the sample collection tube then randomly into the fecal sample in three different sites to collect 50mg of feces, Put the applicator in the tube containing the sample collection swab. Extraction, Close the tube and shake vigorously to mix the sample and the extraction buffer well, distribute 3 drops or 90µl of the mixture in the sampling well of the cassette and set the stopwatch to 10 minutes according to the instructions of the manufacturer of the reagent.

Table 1: Interpretation of Cut-Values for HOMA-IR

Cut-off values	< 1.0	1.9 - 2.9	2.9	>3.0
Signification	Insulin sensible (Low risk)	Insulin resistance (Moderate risk)	Significant insulin resistance (High risk)	Profound insulin resistance

Read the results. Positivity or negativity of the test to prick the sample collection applicator appearance of two bands (one in the control zone and the other in the test zone). The appearance of a single band at the level of the control zone marked the negativity of the test and the *H. pylori*: the test was considered positive by the appearance of a single band at the level of the test zone translated an invalid test.

Ethical Approval

Type two diabetic and non-diabetic patients consulting in the gastroenterology department and of the Internal Medicine of the hospital center University of Brazzaville and spreading to our criteria written informed consent was obtained for each of them. The Brazzaville Health Sciences Research Ethics Committee (CERSA) approved our study.

Statistical Analysis

Excel 2013 software was used for the design and development of the database and RStudio software for data processing. Quantitative variables were expressed as means ± standard deviation, and qualitative variables were expressed as numbers and percentages. The comparison of the qualitative variables was made by the Pearson chi2 test and the comparison of the quantitative variables was made by the Mann-Whitney test.

Limits of Study

The main limitations of our study were the small size of the sample and the period of realization of this work, which was relatively short. The size of sample was small compared to the large cohorts carried out in international studies because all the biological

examinations carried out for the population of our study were at our expense

Results

Table 1 shows the distribution of the prevalence of the study population according to gender in both groups. The overall distribution of the study population was 90 patients; men were 22 in number with prevalence of 28.2% of diabetic patients and 37.4% of non-diabetic patients, women were 36 with a prevalence of 71.8 % of diabetic patients and 62.6 % of non-diabetic patients. The sex ratio was 0.32.

Table 1: Distribution of the Prevalence of the Study Population According to Gender

Gender	Diabetics Subjects n (%)	Non-diabetics Subjects n (%)
Men	8 (28.2)	18 (37.4)
Women	36 (71.8)	28 (62.6)
Total	44 (100)	46 (100)

Table 2 shows the distribution of the prevalence of the study population according to age in both groups. The average age of our study population was 45 ± 14 years with extremes ranging from 18 years and 70 years. The average age of diabetics was 51 ± 11 years and non-diabetics were 40 ± 15 years. The most represented age group was that of 30 to 50 years with a prevalence of 52% in diabetic patients and 34% in non-diabetic patients. Statistical analysis of the results showed no statistically significant difference.

Table 2: Distribution of the Prevalence of the Study Population According to Age

Gender	T2MD(years)	NDT(years)	p-value
Men	50.1 ± 10.1	34.2 ± 8.8	0.023
Women	48.6 ± 8.4	42.3 ± 12.6	0.08
Total	51 ± 11	40 ± 15	0.07

Biochemical Marker Profile HbA_{1c} Distribution in Both Groups

Figure 1 shows HbA_{1c} distribution in both groups of our study population. In non-diabetic patients with *H. pylori*

negative distribution of HbA_{1c} was almost normal with an average of 5.1±0.5 (table 3) and in non-diabetics with *H. pylori* positive the distribution was almost asymmetric with an average of 8.6±0.9 (table 3). This difference was statistically significant. For the case of diabetics, diabetic patients with *H.pylori* negative had an asymmetric distribution in more than 25% of patients and in diabetics with *H. pylori* positive distribution was significant in more than 75% of patients. Statistical analysis showed a statistically significant difference

Blood Sugar Distribution in the Two Groups

Non-diabetic patients with *H. pylori* negative and non-diabetic patients with *H. pylori* positive blood glucose distribution were heterogeneous. In the diabetic group, diabetic patients with *H. pylori* negative had asymmetric distribution with a mean 4.3±1.8 (table3) and T2D patients with *H.pylori* positive the distribution was more heterogeneous with a mean 12.6±2.3 (table2). This difference was statistically significant with a P- value < 0.001

HOMA-IR Index Distribution in Both Groups

Fig.1 shows HOMA-IR index distribution in both groups. In non-diabetic patients with *H. pylori* negative a distribution was almost normal and in non-diabetics with *H. pylori* positive the distribution was almost asymmetric (fig.2). This difference was not significant. Diabetic patients with *H.pylori* negative had an asymmetric distribution and in diabetics with *H. pylori* positive distribution was significant Statistical analysis showed a statistically significant difference with p-value < 0.005.

Insulin Distribution in Both Groups

Figure 11 shows insulin distribution in both groups. Diabetic patients with *H. pylori* negative a distribution was asymmetric and in non-diabetics with *H. pylori* positive, the distribution was similar and homogeneous t (fig.2). This difference was not significant. Diabetic patients with *H.pylori* negative had a symmetric distribution and in diabetics with *H. pylori* positive distribution was no significant Statistical analysis no showed a statistically significant difference.

Table 3: Distribution of Average Carbohydrate Markers According to Infection *H. Pylori*

Variables	Diabetics (n=44)		p-value	Non-Diabetics (n=46)		p-value
	<i>H. pylori</i> Negative	<i>H. pylori</i> Positive		<i>H. pylori</i> Negative	<i>H. pylori</i> Positive	
	(n = 15)	(n = 29)		(n = 24)	(n = 22)	
Blood sugar (mmol/l)	4.3±1.8	12.6±2.3	<0,001	3.9±1.5	9.7±1.0	0.017
HbA _{1c} (%)	5.3±2.01	10.37±2.9	<0,001	5.1±0.5	8.6±0.9	<0.001
Insulinaemia(µU/ml)	6.23±5.23	8.71±3.14	0,801	5.28±3.80	9.7±1.64	0.9
HOMA-IR	1.98±1.12	2.69±1.35	<0,001	0.89±0.58	1.45±0.42	0.020

Table 3: Distribution of Average Carbohydrate Markers According to Infection *H. Pylori*

Variables	Diabetics (n=44)		p-value	Non-Diabetics (n=46)		p-value
	<i>H. pylori</i> Negative (n = 15)	<i>H. pylori</i> Positive (n = 29)		<i>H. pylori</i> Negative (n = 24)	<i>H. pylori</i> Positive (n = 22)	
Blood sugar (mmol/l)	4.3±1.8	12.6±2.3	<0,001	3.9±1.5	9.7±1.0	0.017
HbA _{1c} (%)	5.3±2.01	10.37±2.9	<0,001	5.1±0.5	8.6±0.9	<0.001
Insulinaemia(μU/ml)	6.23±5.23	8.71±3.14	0,801	5.28±3.80	9.7±1.64	0.9
HOMA-IR	1.98±1.12	2.69±1.35	<0,001	0.89±0.58	1.45±0.42	0.020

Table 4: Univariate Logistic Regression Analysis of Insulin, HOMA, Blood Sugar and HbA_{1c} in Diabetic Subjects

Variables	Diabetics Subjects (n=44)				p-value
	<i>H. pylori</i> negative (n=15)	<i>H. pylori</i> positive (n=29)			
		Percentage (%)	Odd ratio (OR)	Confidence interval(95%CI)	
Blood sugar	-	25.81	2.29	1.80-4.5	0.005
HbA _{1c}	-	28.53	3.08	0.87-1.02	0.0018
Insulin	-	1.96	1.02	1.0-0.16	0.02
HOMA-IR	-	30.32	4.4	0.55-0.95	<0.001

Table 5: Univariate Logistic Regression Analysis of Insulin, HOMA, Blood Sugar and HbA_{1c} in Non-Diabetic Subjects

Variables	Diabetics Subjects (n=44)				p-value
	<i>H. pylori</i> negative (n=15)	<i>H. pylori</i> positive (n=29)			
		Percentage (%)	Odd ratio (OR)	Confidence interval(95%CI)	
Blood sugar	-	5.45	1.1	1.01-2.14	0.018
HbA _{1c}	-	10.9	1.35	0.08-1.34	0.03
Insulin	-	4.96	0.51	0.12-1.08	0.3
HOMA-IR	-	20.78	2.4	0.32-1.45	0.0016

Figure 1: Distribution of HbA_{1c} in Both Groups

Figure 2: Distribution of Blood Sugar in Both Groups

Figure 3: Distribution of Insulin in Both Groups

Figure 5: Distribution of Blood Sugar in Both Groups

Discussion

H. pylori infection is the most common infection around the world, particularly in developing countries and its prevalence varies between countries, the prevalence is about 40% in developed and up to 80% in developing countries [15]. The association between *H. pylori* and T2DM was first explored in Simon and *al* study [16]. Recently a meta-analysis suggested that is *H. pylori* infection more frequent in diabetic patients [17]. In this present study, the main aim was to evaluate the possible effects of insulin resistance in diabetes and non-diabetics infected with *H. pylori* infection.

Blood Sugar

The average blood glucose level was 12.6 ± 2.3 mmol/l in infected diabetics and 9.7 ± 1.0 mmol/l in non-diabetics infected with *H. pylori*. Although the results of various studies are contradictory, statistical analysis of our results showed statistically significant differences between infected and uninfected patients. Moreover univariate logistic regression analysis showed that patients T2DM with *H. pylori* had a risk of hyperglycemia with odd ratio 2.29 [95%IC1.80-4.5] with p-value= 0.005 and non-diabetics a risk was zero. Our results are close to those obtained by Mysara and *al* in Egypt who noticed an increase in blood sugar levels in infected diabetic and non-diabetic patients compared to those who were not infected [18].

Glycosylated Hemoglobin (Hb A1C)

Glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) is considered, as indicator of glycemic control, is important for preclinical diagnosis of diabetes, therapeutic monitoring and prevention of vascular complications [19]. *H. pylori* and diabetes are linked in many aspects, but studies on *H. pylori* infection and HbA1c are still relatively few, and there are different conclusions. In some meta-analyses, *H. pylori* were not detected to be related to glycemic control in diabetic population [20-

21]. However, in certain studies, *H. pylori* infection was positively correlated to HbA1c levels [22]. The effects of infection *H. pylori* on glycemic control have been also evaluated by several studies, notably the studies of Jeon and *al* having covered a cohort of 782 Latin Americans and that of Chen and Blaser carried out on the two large national surveys the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANS) III and (NHANS 1999-2000 which had reported new information on the association between the seroprevalence of infection with *H. pylori* and mean levels of Glycosylated Hemoglobin increased in infected patients [21-23]. In this present, the average HbA1c was 10.1 ± 2.9 in diabetic patients 8.6 ± 0.9 in infected non-diabetic patients. Even more univariate logistic regression analysis showed that patients with positive had important risk to have disturbance glycemic control with odd ratio 3.08 [95%IC0.87-1.02] in diabetics patients and odd ratio 1.35 [95% IC0.08-1.34] in non-diabetics patients. Our results corroborate those of Sarita and *al* in India and those Abdullah and *al* in Saudi Arabia who noticed that diabetic and non-diabetic patients infected with *H. pylori* had a disturbance in glycemic control than those who were not infected [25-26]. Therefore, Hsieh and *al* had reported that the high level of HbA1c and the high prevalence of type 2 diabetes were significantly associated in the long term with infection with *H. pylori* [109]. These disturbances could be explained by the fact that *H. pylori* induces a disruption of glucose regulation by a reduction in GLUT4 activity, consequently leading to hyperglycemia and glycemic imbalance given the HbA1C level it is closely linked to that of blood sugar. Another hypothesis is that certain strains *pylori* possess the pathogenicity island (cagPAI) and the Cag protein which could be the cause of the increase in HbA1C level of *H. pylori* infection.

Blood Insulin

Concerning insulinaemia, the average was 8.71 ± 3.14 $\mu\text{U/ml}$ in infected diabetic patients and 9.7 ± 1.64 $\mu\text{U/ml}$ in infected non-diabetic patients. The analysis of our results and the univariate logistic correlation showed no statistically significant difference in our two study groups.

Insulin Resistance

H. pylori infection increases insulin resistance (IR) since it causes a chronic inflammation and affects gastrointestinal hormones function in insulin regulation [3]. The prevalence of IR syndrome and its component is rapidly increasing worldwide because of the ongoing obesity epidemic that significantly increases with age [11]. The first evidence of a direct association between *H. pylori* infection and insulin resistance is that of the study by Aydmir and *al* who noted an increase in insulin resistance index scores in infected patients compared to those who were not infected [3].

Means of the insulin resistance index were determined in the study population using the methodology used by Jamschid and *al*, that of Longo-Mbenza and *al*, Aydemir and *al* [28-27-3]. Analysis of our results showed that HOMA-IR scores were high in infected diabetic patients with an average of 2.69 ± 1.35 . However, HOMA-IR scores were slightly elevated in infected non-diabetic patients with an average of 1.45 ± 0.42 .

Although the level of insulin resistance index scores is associated with the pathogenesis of diabetes. The correlation of HOMA-IR means and *H. pylori* infection in our study showed that diabetic patients infected with *H. pylori* had a 4.4 fold increased risk of developing insulin resistance compared to those who were not infected and 2.4 fold for those without diabetes. Our results are close to those obtained by Sato and *al* as well as HOMA-IR scores were more IR. ≥ 2.5 [29]. This could be explained by the fact that the lipopolysaccharide of *H. pylori* stimulates Toll-like receptors which increase the secretion of pro-inflammatory cytokines including interleukin 8 and tumor necrosis factor (TNF-) which cause phosphorylation of serine residues on insulin receptors thus preventing the interaction between insulin and its receptor therefore insulin resistance and also alterations of gastric hormones involved in insulin regulation. Shabana and *al* in Egypt who had noticed that the elevated levels in patients infected with *H. pylori* [30].

Conclusion

To summarize the results of our study showed clearly that *H. pylori* infection is associated with negative effects in T2DM and non-diabetics patients. Futures studies on a large number of patients to prove the association between *H. pylori* and IR and to explore the benefit of *H. pylori* eradication in reduction of IR.

Conflicts of Interest

There were no conflicts of interest.

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We declare that we have not received any financial support or sponsorship.

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